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Depiction of community in European Art: *companilismo* in Italy and
sentimiento di comunidad in Spain

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INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized world, the issue of preserving and rethinking local identity is becoming particularly relevant. One of the important areas of research in this area is the study of how artistic practices reflect and construct the image of the community. The image of the community in European art is multidimensional, as it not only conveys aesthetic ideas, but also serves as a means of preserving historical memory, forming regional traditions, and emphasizing the uniqueness of individual socio-cultural spaces.

The topic of the thesis "Images of Community in European Art: Campanilismo in Italy and Sentimenti de Comunidad in Spain" is aimed at a comprehensive study of two phenomena that have become peculiar markers of local identity in Europe. In Italy, the concept of campanilismo is closely connected with the history of city-states, when each city had its own unique political, economic and cultural autonomy, which was reflected in the images of local heroes, patron saints and architectural ensembles. At the same time, in Spain, the concept of Sentimenti de Comunidad developed in the context of the early unification of kingdoms, while retaining a deep regional connotation. These two phenomena, despite their certain similarities, have different historical development, scope of influence and methods of visual representation, which is the basis for conducting a comparative analysis.

Preservation of local identity is becoming an extremely important task in the era of globalization, when cultural unification and mass communication can lead to the loss of unique features of local communities. In this context, art acts as a key tool that allows not only to preserve historical heritage, but also to rethink it in the context of modern challenges. The study of campanilismo and sentimiento de comunidad allows for a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of formation of collective memory and local patriotism, as well as their impact on modern cultural policy. Thanks to this research, it is possible to identify common and distinctive features between different

European cultures, which contributes to the dialogue between tradition and modernization.

The main goal of the work is to study the features of the depiction of community in European art using the example of two phenomena: campanilismo in Italy and sentimiento de comunidad in Spain, as well as to conduct a comparative analysis of their visual representation. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

- To analyze the historical and cultural context in which the phenomena of campanilismo and sentimiento de comunidad arose and developed.
- Consider the artistic language and symbolism used to represent these phenomena in art.
- Conduct a detailed analysis of individual works and artists who became carriers of these ideas.
- To conduct a comparative analysis between the Italian campanilismo and the Spanish sentimiento de comunidad, to identify their common features and differences.
- To determine the impact of these phenomena on the formation of regional and national identity in the context of modern globalization.

The work uses an interdisciplinary approach, which includes methods of historical and art analysis, comparative research, content analysis of visual symbolism and interpretation of artistic images. The theoretical basis is based on the works of prominent researchers, in particular Benedict Anderson, who in his book *Imagined Communities* (Anderson, 1983) outlines the concept of national imagined communities, as well as on the works of Edward Gombrich, Peter Burke and others who studied the development of culture and art in the context of social processes. The use of such sources allows us to reveal the depth of historical processes that laid the foundation for the emergence of the phenomena of campanilismo and sentimiento de comunidad.

Methodologically, the research is based on the analysis of works of art from different eras - from medieval frescoes and Renaissance paintings to modern installations and multimedia projects. Thanks to comparative analysis, it is possible to

identify both the specific features of the visual language of each phenomenon and their common features, which indicate universal mechanisms of local identity formation in Europe.

Research on this topic is of great practical importance for several reasons. First, it contributes to a better understanding of the processes underlying the formation of local identity, as well as their impact on modern society. Second, the results of the work can be used in cultural policy to develop strategies for preserving cultural heritage and stimulating regional development. Third, the data obtained can become the basis for further research in the field of cultural studies, art history, sociology and history, which will allow us to delve deeper into the issues of the European cultural mosaic.

The work consists of three main sections, which systematically highlight the key aspects of the research. The first section is devoted to the theoretical and methodological foundations of the study of the phenomenon of community in European art. It examines conceptual approaches to the concept of “community”, the historical and cultural prerequisites for the emergence of *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad*, as well as the research methodology, which includes historical analysis, a comparative approach and content analysis of visual symbolism.

The second chapter focuses on the analysis of *campanilismo* in Italian art. It examines in detail the historical and cultural context of Italy, the formation of city-state traditions, the influence of the Renaissance, as well as the features of the artistic language and symbolism that accompany the phenomenon of *campanilismo*. Special attention is paid to the study of individual works and works by prominent Italian artists that illustrate this theme.

The third chapter is devoted to the analysis of *sentimiento de comunidad* in Spanish art and a comparative analysis with *campanilismo*. This chapter examines the historical and cultural context of Spain, which has shaped the features of regional identity, and analyzes the visual features and artistic symbolism characteristic of the Spanish phenomenon of “sense of community”. The comparative analysis allows us to identify both common features and significant differences between the Italian and

Spanish approaches to the formation of collective identity, which reveals new aspects of the cultural diversity of Europe.

It is expected that the results of the study will contribute to a better understanding not only of the historical processes that laid the foundation for the emergence of *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad*, but also of modern trends related to the preservation of local identity in the context of globalization. The scientific novelty of the work lies in the integrated approach to the analysis of these phenomena, which allows combining traditional historical and art methods with modern interpretations and comparative studies. The results obtained may open new perspectives in the study of the mechanisms of constructing collective memory and contribute to the development of the theory of cultural identity in the European context.

Thus, this thesis aims to explore how local identity is reflected and preserved in Italy and Spain through various artistic practices and symbolic means. The analysis of *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad* allows not only to trace the evolution of artistic traditions, but also to find out how these traditions influence the modern understanding of the local community and its interaction with global cultural processes. The results of the study can be an important contribution to understanding the role of art as a means of social communication and a tool for constructing cultural heritage.

Successfully solving the tasks will contribute to the formation of new conceptual approaches to the study of collective memory, identity and cultural autonomy, and will also help determine how local traditions can adapt and develop in response to the challenges of the modern world. Therefore, the research will not only contribute to the development of academic thought in the field of art and cultural studies, but will also have practical significance for the preservation of unique regional traditions, which are an integral part of the European cultural heritage.

This introduction outlines the scope and relevance of the study, defines its purpose, objectives, methodological framework, and expected results, which creates a solid foundation for further consideration of the phenomena of *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad* in the following sections of the work.

CHAPTER 1. THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF RESEARCHING THE PHENOMENON OF COMMUNITY

1.1. Conceptual approaches to the concept of "community"

The concept of "community" (Latin *communitas*) is one of the central concepts in the social sciences and humanities. Its content implies a certain association of individuals who have common values, interests or cultural heritage (Anderson, 1983). In the broadest sense, "community" encompasses various forms of collectivity - from small groups (family, professional) to large-scale national or cross-border formations. However, in the context of art and cultural studies, the question of how this collective identity and unity is visualized and interpreted through artistic images, symbols and aesthetic practices is of particular interest.

The origins of the scientific study of the phenomenon of "community" are usually associated with the works of the German sociologist Ferdinand Tönnies (1887), who distinguished between *Gemeinschaft* (the deep, "natural" bonds inherent in small groups) and *Gesellschaft* (the rational social relations of modern industrial societies). Although Tönnies's work was not directly devoted to art, his views laid the foundation for further research on the nature of collective bonds and how they are reflected in various aspects of culture.

During the twentieth century, the concept of "community" has acquired a more tangible political and ideological dimension. In particular, Benedict Anderson, in his book *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism* (1983), emphasizes that nations as "imagined communities" are constructed through symbolic practices - language, rituals, as well as through visual and literary narratives. This approach allows us to see that any "community" requires certain symbols and practices of representation that strengthen the sense of unity.

In European art of the 20th and 21st centuries, interest in the theme of community is inextricably linked to historical upheavals (world wars, civil conflicts, the emergence of supranational entities such as the European Union). This stimulated artists, curators and art historians to explore issues of collective identity, historical memory and local specificities in a single European context (Gombrich, 2000). In this way, the depiction of community in European art turns out to be a multidimensional process, encompassing local specificities and pan-European dialogue.

In the context of European art, community performs several important functions. First, it is a function of identification: it allows individuals to realize themselves as part of a larger whole - a city, a region or a nation. Through artistic works (painting, architecture, sculpture, cinema) symbols and signs are fixed, which become markers of collective memory (Hobsbawm, Ranger, 1983). Second, community performs an integration function, uniting people around a certain project or tradition, for example, festivals, carnivals or religious holidays. In Italy, such integrative factors are often the celebration of the day of the patron saint of a particular city, while in Spain - celebrations associated with regional patrons or historical events (Ginsborg, 1990; Moreno, 1997).

The third important function is the function of social control. Within a community, there are norms and standards that determine what is acceptable and what is not. These norms are often traced in art: artists working in a certain region may consciously or subconsciously take into account local aesthetic standards. For example, Italian Renaissance masters often referred to local religious cults or patrons to express the idea of community (Paoletti, Radke, 2005). At the same time, in the 20th century,

a number of Spanish artists referred to national and regional identity through images of Saint James or the Virgin Mary (Cirlot, 1992).

Finally, the function of symbolic reproduction: a community not only maintains the status quo, but also reproduces itself across generations through symbols, rituals, myths, and ideas about "us" and "others." This process is reflected in art through themes that appear again and again, transforming according to historical context. It is through such images and themes that art becomes a powerful tool for legitimizing and popularizing community ideas (Freedberg, 1989).

European art, despite its diversity, has always dealt with local, regional and national specificities (Burke, 1972). From early medieval miniatures depicting scenes from the life of monastic communities to modern installations reflecting ideas of a united Europe, artists have used visual means to actualize whether religious, secular or ethnic community. In this sense, the "community" becomes not only the object of the image, but also a kind of matrix of the creative process, since it was often the community that commissioned and financed works of art (for example, the communal councils of city-states in the medieval Italian tradition).

During the Renaissance (15th–16th centuries), the patriotism of city-states (Florence, Venice, Genoa) stimulated the emergence of large public commissions that emphasized local pride, and this was in fact the forerunner of what later became known as *campanilismo* (Paoletti, Radke, 2005). In Spain in the 16th–17th centuries, during the so-called "Golden Age" (*Siglo de Oro*), monarchs and aristocracy contributed to the formation of an ideology of Catholic community, which, however, had different regional shades - from Castile to Andalusia (Brown, Elliott, 1991). Thus began to emerge the basis for the modern *sentimiento de comunidad*.

Thus, the understanding of community in European art cannot be reduced exclusively to social or political aspects. It includes both ethical dimensions (what is valuable for a given group of people) and aesthetic dimensions (how these values are embodied in form, color, composition). Therefore, considering the concept of community requires an interdisciplinary approach: a combination of tools from sociology, history, philosophy, and art criticism.

1.2. Theoretical foundations of campanilismo and sentimiento de comunidad

The term campanilismo comes from the Italian word campanile (bell tower) and is traditionally associated with pride in one's native land, that is, with a sense of belonging to a specific area, "under the shadow of the bell tower" of which a person grew up. Historically, this phenomenon arose in medieval Italian city-states, where political and social power was closely linked to local institutions - the commune, guilds and church structures (Ginzburg, 1980). In cities such as Florence, Siena, Bologna or Genoa, the feeling of patriotism towards one's own city was so strong that it influenced the formation of individual cultural and artistic canons. Each city sought to emphasize its own uniqueness, which was reflected both in architecture (the construction of town halls, palaces, unique bell towers) and in orders to artists or sculptors, who were called upon to immortalize certain pages of the city's history.

The Italian city-states of the Middle Ages and the Renaissance actually functioned as separate political entities. Their status was confirmed by economic power (trade, banking), political independence and the richness of local traditions. As John M. Najemy notes in his study of Florentine history, it was the local elite that financed large-scale artistic projects to demonstrate the power and prestige of the city (Najemy, 2006). In Florence, this was the Medici family, in Siena, the influential Tolomei or Salimbeni families, in Genoa, the Doria family, etc. Such orders contributed to the emergence of powerful art schools, specific stylistic features, which later became the pride of the townspeople. It is because of this that the phenomenon of campanilismo became so closely embedded in the cultural consciousness of Italy.

Unlike nationalism in the modern sense, campanilismo does not necessarily claim political independence for a city or region. Its essence is to emphasize the unique path of development of a certain territorial entity (on the scale of a city, province or small region), its historical achievements, cultural treasures and traditions that belong to "their own". In art, this was often manifested through references to heroic pages of

the city's history, for example, to significant battles or victories, portraits of local saints and patrons, as well as literary characters associated with a specific area (Paoletti, Radke, 2005). Thus, in Siena, where the story of the Virgin Mary (Madonna delle Grazie) is especially popular, artists of the 13th–14th centuries (in particular Duccio di Buoninsegna, Simone Martini, the Lorenzetti brothers) created altarpieces and frescoes that glorified the Virgin Mary as the patroness of the city. This was not only a religious gesture, but also a powerful artistic affirmation of local pride and belief in the special grace that the Virgin Mary shows specifically to the people of Siena.

In the modern era, especially during the Risorgimento (19th century), campanilismo gained a larger dimension, entering into dialogue with the ideas of a pan-Italian nation. The Risorgimento was a movement for the unification of Italy, when a number of political figures, including Camillo Benso di Cavour, Giuseppe Mazzini and Giuseppe Garibaldi, tried to create a single state from many disparate entities - kingdoms, duchies, republics. However, even after the formal unification of Italy in 1861 and the proclamation of Rome as the capital in 1871, regional pride still remained a powerful factor influencing the formation of local identity (Duggan, 2013). Many cities, previously accustomed to autonomy, preserved their own dialects, local customs and even in the new political system continued to assert the uniqueness of “their” historical heritage.

In the 20th century, the process of industrialization and modernization exacerbated the issue of local identities: large-scale migrations took place within the country, residents of southern regions moved en masse to the north in search of work. Despite this, as cultural scientists and anthropologists note, it is thanks to campanilismo that local communities have maintained their uniqueness even in the era of globalization (Ginsborg, 1990). In modern Italy, one can see vivid manifestations of this trend: from festivals in honor of the city's patron saint to the use of specific dialects on local television. All this remains a form of "soft" resistance to unification, emphasizing pride in local cuisine, history, artistic traditions and even sporting achievements (for example, football teams). The very name campanilismo refers to the bell tower, which often serves as the most visible symbol of the city, dominating the

cityscape. For example, in Florence, Giotto's bell tower or the dome of Santa Maria del Fiore, in Siena, the Torre del Mangia tower at the Palazzo Pubblico: each of these monuments outlines the "silhouette" of the city and symbolizes its historical uniqueness.

From an art-historical point of view, campanilismo is expressed through special attention to plots related to local festivals, historical events or legends that took place in a particular city. A striking example is the famous palii - traditional races in Siena, which have been going on since the Middle Ages and are still held in the central square of Piazza del Campo. This event has become so significant for the collective identity of the Sieneese that its depiction can be found on numerous frescoes and canvases, starting from the 15th-16th centuries. They convey not only the excitement of the sport, but also the spirit of competition between the contradas - districts of the city, each of which has its own patron saint, coat of arms and ancient traditions. Thus, the palio becomes an aesthetic representation of campanilismo: it embodies the idea that "our" contrada or "our" city is the center of pride, identity and passionate competition.

Another example is the Sieneese school of painting (13th–14th centuries), which is often contrasted with the Florentine school. While Florence was dominated by a more rational and monumental style (with prominent representatives such as Giotto and later Masaccio), Sieneese artists (Duccio, Martini, the Lorenzetti brothers) gravitated towards refined linearity, refined color, and a special sensuality of religious subjects (Burke, 1972). This was a conscious emphasis on their own, "Sieneese," aesthetics, which distinguished the city from neighboring Florence, an eternal rival. Thus, campanilismo was reflected in artistic techniques, in the choice of subjects, and in the maintenance of certain canons of beauty and composition.

In the case of Spain, the concept of sentimiento de comunidad — "feeling of community" — has its own, no less deep, historical roots. They grow from the formation of various kingdoms on the Iberian Peninsula (Castile, Aragon, Navarre, Granada, etc.) and their subsequent integration into a single monarchy (15th–16th centuries) (Kamen, 1964). Unlike Italy, where the power structure remained politically fragmented for a long time until unification in the 19th century, in Spain the process of

consolidation of the central monarchy took place earlier, especially after the Catholic Kings — Ferdinand II of Aragon and Isabella I of Castile (late 15th–early 16th centuries). However, even within this single monarchy, each region — Catalonia, the Basque Country, Andalusia, Galicia, etc. — retained its own cultural traditions, dialects, and legal customs. This formed a complex balance between central authority and regional autonomy, which further influenced the perception of the unity and diversity of the Spanish nation.

According to a number of researchers, *sentimiento de comunidad* in modern discourse is often identified with forms of self-awareness of individual national-regional communities. These are Catalans, Basques, Andalusians and other communities that, while preserving their own identity, still recognize their belonging to the wider Spanish state community (Moreno, 1997). In art, this is manifested in the wealth of artistic practices: Catalan modernist art (Gaudi, Domènech i Montaner, Puig and Cadafalc), Andalusian folkloric and religious traditions (Feria de Abril in Seville, Holy Week processions - *Semana Santa*), Basque avant-garde (Eduardo Chillida), etc. Each of these cultural trends not only represents its region, but also to a certain extent constructs its “difference” from the rest of Spain.

Andalusian culture, for example, is one of the most expressive in terms of visual and musical tradition. The celebration of the Feria de Abril (April Fair) in Seville is accompanied by parades, the installation of brightly decorated tents, horse processions, flamenco and traditional cuisine. Posters and souvenirs dedicated to this event often display typical Andalusian motifs: female figures in colorful dresses, patterns that echo the Moorish heritage, elements of Arab architecture, etc. All this indicates the specificity of the region, its historical past, associated with the long existence of Muslim emirates in this territory (until 1492). For the inhabitants of Andalusia, such attributes symbolize not only festivity, but also a deep sense of collective belonging, that is, *sentimiento de comunidad*.

Catalan art, in turn, has a rich modernist heritage: the name of Antonio Gaudí is known throughout the world for his “organic” architecture (in particular, the famous *Sagrada Família*), and José Puig y Cadafalc became famous for developing building

designs that combined neo-Gothic, modern elements and traditional Catalan motifs (Cirlot, 1992). This luxury of forms, expression of lines, references to the medieval history of Catalonia and to the folklore of the region have become cultural markers that Catalans feel as “their own”, different from the Castilian canon. This gives rise to the idea of a Catalan “community” within a unified Spain, constantly balancing between the desire for political and cultural autonomy and integration into the national space.

It is also important to note that the Spanish “sense of community” has had a strong religious undertone for centuries: Catholicism has played a central role in the spiritual life of the country, starting at least from the end of the Reconquista (late 15th century), when the last Muslim stronghold in Granada was taken by royal troops. This led to the emergence and flourishing of a large number of religious buildings, iconographic images, and temple sculpture (Lannon, 1987). For example, sculptural images of the Virgin Mary or saints are carried through the streets of cities and villages during festive processions, embodying a collective religious identity. Such events, in particular the Holy Week processions in Seville or Malaga, gather a huge number of believers and tourists who become witnesses to an event deeply rooted in history and tradition. In these spectacles, the unity of the community is very tangible, which is what the *sentimiento de comunidad* represents.

At the same time, researchers emphasize that the *sentimiento de comunidad* in Spain goes far beyond religion - it is based on historical myths (the Reconquista as the reconquest of Christian lands from Muslims), on such legendary figures as El Cid, on the phenomenon of the “Catholic Kings” Ferdinand and Isabella, who symbolized the unification of the peninsula (Kamen, 1964). The literary tradition also plays an important role: Cervantes (author of “Don Quixote”), Lope de Vega, Calderón de la Barca consolidated images and themes in the culture that are equally recognizable in Castile and other regions. However, each of these regions can reinterpret these symbols differently, introduce its own accents and expand the semantic circle around them.

In the 20th century, Spain went through a difficult period under the dictatorship of General Francisco Franco (1939–1975), when regional specificities were often suppressed by official policies of unitarism and centralism. After Franco’s death and

the transition to democracy, a large-scale decentralization took place: the 1978 Constitution recognized a number of autonomous communities (*Comunidades Autónomas*), each of which received certain self-governing powers (Moreno, 1997). This process contributed to the actualization of the *sentimiento de comunidad* at the official level, as regional governments began to support their own languages (Catalan, Galician, Basque) and cultural practices (festivals, exhibitions, local initiatives). In contemporary art, we observe an even more interesting picture: young artists and photographers are increasingly turning to local narratives, intertwining them with global themes of ecology, migration, or urbanization (Gómez, 2009). This creates a multi-vector space where the “sense of community” acts as an identifying factor, but at the same time does not deny involvement in pan-European or global processes.

Despite the fact that *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad* have different historical origins and are expressed in different cultural contexts, there are a number of common features between them. First of all, both phenomena are aimed at strengthening collective identity and emphasizing the uniqueness of a particular community within larger political entities (Italy or Spain, respectively). Their roots go back to local traditions, historical events, legends, as well as religious or secular rituals. Artistic practices — from frescoes on the walls of city halls to contemporary performances or video installations — become a means of materializing these traditions. City coats of arms, images of patrons, folklore plots, church rituals, architectural dominants (bell towers, cathedrals) — all these are visual components that nourish the sense of “we” among the inhabitants of a certain territory (Anderson, 1983).

At the same time, it is worth noting the differences between these two phenomena. While *campanilismo* can sometimes be more limited, rather urban or provincial in scope (it is about pride specifically for Florence, Siena, Genoa or any other city), *sentimiento de comunidad* often extends to the entire region, which can include several cities, towns and different social groups. In Italy, regional pride has deep roots in the era of city republics, while in Spain a similar feeling is often formed by a combination of historical centralization with subsequent periods of autonomization (Kamen, 1964; Moreno, 1997). Therefore, for example, in some areas

of Spain (Catalonia, the Basque Country) the community can have a clearly expressed political component - we are talking about movements for increased autonomy or even independence. In Italy, despite the activities of individual movements (for example, the “Liga of the North”, now known as “Lega”), campanilismo most often remains at the level of symbolic defense of local customs and historical heritage, not always turning into a large-scale separatist project.

For the art historian, both of these phenomena are extremely important, as they influence the choice of subjects by artists, the form of commissions, iconography, as well as the interaction of the artist with society. Understanding the theoretical foundations of campanilismo and sentimiento de comunidad helps to penetrate deeper into the semantic world of works created in these cultural contexts. The researcher must take into account that each work of art is “embedded” in a certain social environment, and it is important for the artist (or the commissioner) to emphasize the connection with local history, memory, or regional myths. Thus, even at first glance, narrowly local subjects can reflect universal ideas related to collective identity and the search for cultural “roots”.

The modern globalized era poses new challenges to campanilismo and sentimiento de comunidad. On the one hand, the openness of borders and the development of mass tourism make local traditions a “commodity” for external consumption. This can be seen in Italy, when mass tourist flows visit the Palio in Siena or the Carnival events in Venice; a commercial component appears, affecting the authenticity of traditions. In Spain, tourists are similarly eager to go to Las Fallas in Valencia or San Fermín in Pamplona (the famous bull festival), transforming ancient folk rituals into globally popular attractions. On the other hand, it is these manifestations that allow local residents to maintain a sense of shared history and pride. After all, moderate “cultural marketing” can be an incentive for the revival of forgotten crafts, dishes, rituals, the preservation of architectural heritage, etc. In such a situation, campanilismo and sentimiento de comunidad become objects of “awakened” interest, when communities begin to actively defend their right to historical uniqueness and cultural heritage in a world of standard chain hotels and standardized entertainment.

Thus, campanilismo and sentimiento de comunidad can in no way be considered as atavisms of the past: they continue to influence contemporary society and art, serving at the same time as a driving force for the preservation of local identity and a creative impulse for artists who seek to rethink their own traditions. In the 21st century, when a significant part of humanity lives in large cities and is influenced by global cultural models, the ideas of a “small homeland”, a unique history and a common myth acquire new relevance. It is in art - from painting and architecture to performance and digital installations - that we can observe the rethinking of old symbols and the birth of new images that embody both pride in one’s place and openness to the world.

In summary, we can say that campanilismo in Italy and sentimiento de comunidad in Spain represent two close, yet specific phenomena, which have different historical backgrounds and different spatial “scales”. They are an integral part of the European cultural heritage and largely determine how the inhabitants of certain cities or regions see, feel and represent themselves through art. Knowledge of these phenomena helps the researcher and the wider public to better understand the processes of collective identity formation, the role of the artist in society, the specifics of regional traditions and the possibilities of integrating local culture into the global context.

Given the current trends of globalization, which often lead to standardization and cultural unification, campanilismo and sentimiento de comunidad continue to act as powerful factors of identity. Artistic practices inspired by these phenomena also enrich the global cultural landscape, offering unique visions and approaches to understanding history, memory, traditions and contemporary challenges. In this sense, the historical roots and contemporary transformation of both phenomena deserve in-depth study, as they allow us to see how, through the prism of local experience, identity is intertwined with universal values, and art becomes not only a mirror of social processes, but also a tool for their rethinking.

1.3. Research methodology

To study the depiction of community in European art, in particular the phenomena of *campanilismo* in Italy and *sentimiento de comunidad* in Spain, it is extremely important to apply an interdisciplinary approach. Art itself does not exist in a vacuum; its formation is directly related to historical, social, political and religious factors that influence each era (Burke, 1972). Therefore, to achieve a full understanding of the depiction of community, it is necessary to involve tools from various fields of knowledge, such as history, sociology, anthropology, cultural studies and philosophy. Such an approach allows us to take into account the multiplicity of contexts and provide a comprehensive interpretation of the phenomenon.

Sociological analysis allows us to examine how notions of community function in society. It helps to identify the mechanisms that support or transform these notions, revealing both formal and informal institutions that influence social organization. According to Hobsbawm and Ranger (1983), traditions and symbols play a key role in the construction of national and regional notions, which over time become “invented traditions.” These traditions, although historically based, are often reconstructed in modern conditions in order to confirm collective identity.

A historical approach is necessary to reconstruct the origins and dynamics of processes related to *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad*. Through the analysis of historical documents, literary sources and archival materials, it is possible to trace how symbols and iconographic motifs that reflect community changed. For example, the research of Kamen (1964) and Duggan (2013) allows us to see how, in the process of unification of Italy and the formation of a single Spanish state, ancient regional traditions retained their relevance, despite the centralization of power.

Anthropological research focuses on the analysis of rituals, traditions, and symbols, which are often reflected in visual art. For example, Moreno's (1997) extensive ethnographic research shows that traditional rites and rituals in the regions of Spain reflect a deep sense of community that is passed down from generation to generation. These rituals, such as the celebration of festivals, processions, and folk

festivals, not only create a unique cultural code, but also become a powerful means of preserving historical memory.

Art historical methods, including the analysis of form, style, iconography, and composition, are an integral part of the study, as they allow us to reveal how the image of a community is visualized in works of art. For example, the methodology of Erwin Panofsky (Panofsky, 1982) conducts iconographic and iconological analysis, which helps to reveal hidden meanings, associations, and cultural codes used by artists. This approach allows us not only to describe what is depicted, but also to reveal why these images had such significance for a particular community in a particular historical era.

One of the key methods in this study is historical-genetic analysis. It allows us to trace the development of artistic traditions in dynamics, to determine how symbols and iconographic motifs associated with the idea of community changed under the influence of broad historical processes. For example, analyzing the processes of unification of Italy, we can find out how local symbols of cities changed their meaning from a means of resistance to feudal power to a marker of regional identity. Also, in the case of Spain, historical-genetic analysis allows us to reveal how the process of the Reconquista and the subsequent centralization of power influenced the preservation of regional traditions, which resulted in the concept of *sentimiento de comunidad* (Ginsborg, 1990; Kamen, 1964).

Another relevant approach is comparative analysis. Comparing the two phenomena – *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad* – one can find both common features and significant differences. Common to both is the desire to preserve local identity and confirm historical memory through the use of symbols, rituals and traditions. However, the difference is that *campanilismo* has a more urban character, while *sentimiento de comunidad* covers a wider regional context. Such a comparative approach allows not only to reveal the specificity of each phenomenon, but also to show how ideas of local community take on different forms in different cultural contexts, which confirms their universality in the European cultural heritage (Anderson, 1983; Hobsbawm & Ranger, 1983).

To study how community is represented in works of art, it is advisable to apply content analysis of visual symbolism. This method allows you to systematically investigate which symbols and images are used to convey the idea of community. First, it is necessary to identify key symbols: these can be city coats of arms, images of patrons, historical events or shared rituals that evoke associations with a particular community. Second, it is important to classify the works by medium – painting, frescoes, architecture, sculpture, graphics – to determine in which of them the theme of local or regional pride is most vividly reflected.

Next, iconographic and iconological analysis should be applied in the spirit of Panofsky's methodology (Panofsky, 1982). This allows not only to decipher visual codes, but also to establish a connection between the depicted images and textual, liturgical or folklore sources. It is also important to conduct a comparative interpretation, involving historical documents, chronicles, acts of ordering works of art or correspondence between artists. This approach allows for a deeper understanding of how social elites and the wider community influenced the formation of the visual image of the community.

The method of content analysis of visual symbolism is particularly effective when combined with an analysis of historical context and sociocultural processes. This approach allows us to determine not only what is depicted, but also why these images became important to society in a particular historical period (Freedberg, 1989).

Regarding contemporary manifestations of *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad*, participant observation and semi-structured interviews with artists, curators, and local community members are important methods. Borrowed from cultural anthropology, these methods allow us to explore the living processes of collective identity formation by directly immersing ourselves in the practices of creating and “consuming” art. During regional festivals in Tuscany or Andalusia, for example, it is possible to directly observe which symbols prevail, how they are perceived by locals and tourists, and what role local artists and artisans play (Gómez, 2009).

It is also important to consider the ethical aspects of researching topics related to local or regional pride. There is a risk of reification of the culture of a particular community, when the researcher, due to the desire to emphasize “identity”, may simplify or distort real processes. This is especially true for Spain, where regionalism is often intertwined with political movements, which makes the topic politically sensitive (Kamen, 1964). Therefore, the approach to research should be considered, avoiding stereotypes and overly politicized generalizations.

Finally, the correctness of interpretations is a key condition for successful research. When analyzing religious symbols or traditions that may have profound meaning for a particular community, the researcher must base his conclusions on empirical data - observations, analysis of textual and historical sources, and not only on his own prejudices. Only such a comprehensive approach allows us to obtain a reliable picture of the processes of community formation in art (Freedberg, 1989).

Thus, the use of an interdisciplinary approach that combines sociological, historical, anthropological and art-historical methods allows us to explore the image of a community in all its complexity. This approach allows us to take into account not only the formal aspects of works of art, but also the socio-cultural processes that influence their creation. A comparative analysis between the phenomena of *campanilismo* in Italy and *sentimiento de comunidad* in Spain allows us to identify universal mechanisms for the formation of local identity, as well as the specifics of their implementation in different cultural and historical contexts. Thus, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of how art constructs and maintains collective memory and how symbolic images become carriers of cultural heritage in the conditions of modern globalization.

This methodological approach allows not only to describe the image of a community, but also to analyze how it is transformed under the influence of changes in society, how it evolves from classical artistic traditions to modern media practices. Thus, interdisciplinarity provides a multidimensional analysis that opens new perspectives for understanding the role of art in the formation of cultural identity and provides a solid foundation for further research in this field.

Thus, the described approach to the study of the image of a community allows us to take into account all aspects - historical, social, political, religious and cultural - that influence the formation of collective memory, identity and local pride. The use of historical-genetic, comparative and content analysis of visual symbolism, as well as methods of embedded observation and interviewing, creates a comprehensive methodological framework that can answer the key research questions. This allows us not only to reveal what exactly is reflected in works of art, but also to find out why these images became so important for specific communities in certain historical periods.

CHAPTER 2. ANALYSIS OF CAMPANILISMO IN ITALIAN ART

2.1. Historical and cultural context of Italy

The phenomenon of campanilismo in Italy is inextricably linked to a unique historical and cultural situation that arose as a result of prolonged political fragmentation and the formation of city-states. From the Middle Ages until the end of the 18th century, Italy was a conglomerate of diverse political entities: republics (e.g. Genoese, Venetian, Florentine), duchies (Milan, Modena, Ferrara), kingdoms (Neapolitan and Sicilian), etc. For a long time, these entities were in a state of rivalry and alliances that were constantly changing (Duggan, 2013). In political terms, this meant that cities often sought to assert their own independence and influence, even when they recognized the nominal authority of the Pope or the Holy Roman Emperor.

Unlike the centralized monarchies of England or France, Italy developed through the active participation of urban communes in state administration. In cities such as Florence, Siena, Bologna, Perugia, and Lucca, residents elected representatives to municipal councils, established their own statutes, and developed trade and banking (Ginzburg, 1980). This political fragmentation, which had negative consequences (constant wars, complex diplomatic relations), also contributed to the fact that cultural competition between cities fueled artistic and scientific activity. Cities competed not only in the military or economic spheres, but also in the construction of palaces,

temples, and universities, in the creation of libraries, and in the financing of prominent artists. This competitive spirit laid the foundation for the emergence of vibrant local schools of painting, architecture, and sculpture (Paoletti and Radke, 2005).

Formally, this situation arose in the High Middle Ages (11th–13th centuries), when city-states strengthened their autonomy from feudal lords. The first guilds, workshops, and professional associations appeared, which influenced urban politics. Even then, urban communities began to form their own type of identity: a resident of Florence perceived himself as a “Florentine” rather than a subject of an abstract king or emperor (Najemy, 2006). The significance of this fact is difficult to overestimate: it was during this period that the psychological and cultural foundations of *campanilismo* — devotion to a specific “small homeland,” personified by the symbol of the local bell tower (*campanile*) — were born.

The Renaissance (15th–16th centuries) was a period of the heyday of city-states and solidified the idea that each city had its own historical mission, cultural vocation and unique heritage. The feeling of separateness and rivalry was especially evident between Florence, Milan, Venice and Rome. All these centers competed for the most talented artists: Leonardo da Vinci, Michelangelo Buonarroti, Raphael Santi, Donatello and other masters often changed employers, moving from city to city, fulfilling orders from rulers or municipal councils (Paoletti, Radke, 2005, p. 56). For example, the authorities of Florence (the Medici dynasty) financed the painting of chapels, the construction of cathedrals and public buildings, and promoted the formation of the Academy of Arts in order to enhance the city's reputation as the “new Athens”.

During this period, *campanilismo* manifested itself through several mechanisms:

1. Patronage. The Medici, Gonzaga, Este, Sforza, Visconti, Strozzi, etc. families acted as patrons of artists, sculptors and poets in order to glorify their name and at the same time glorify the city. In the case of Florence, the glory of the city was inextricably linked to the patronage of Cosimo de' Medici the Elder and his descendants, who involved artists in the creation of unique cultural projects (Najemy, 2006, p. 102).

2. Architectural competition. Cities built magnificent cathedrals and bell towers, symbolizing not only piety but also the prestige of the city. A striking example is the construction of the dome of the Florence Cathedral of Santa Maria del Fiore (architect Filippo Brunelleschi) or the development of the central square in Siena (Piazza del Campo), where the Torre del Mangia tower rises. These buildings became “calling cards”, visible from afar, and emphasized the uniqueness of the community (Burke, 1972, p. 77).
3. The development of local schools of art. Siena, for example, developed its own school of art (Duccio, Simone Martini, the Lorenzetti brothers), which was often contrasted with the Florentine school. The Sienese school was distinguished by its refined linearity, greater commitment to the Gothic tradition, and vivid color schemes—all of which reflected the character of the local culture (Burke, 1972).

Such intense competition also built strong local identities. For example, the Florentines were proud of their tradition of republican rule, while the Venetians were proud of their aristocratic republic and their unrivaled success in maritime trade. These prides were reflected in propaganda works, frescoes, and engravings, where the city was presented in an idealized form, often with allegorical figures (Paoletti, Radke, 2005, p. 112).

The Counter-Reformation period (16th–17th centuries) brought about adjustments to the political and religious map of Italy. After the Council of Trent (1545–1563), the Catholic Church increased its influence, which was reflected in culture: the Baroque style spread, religious subjects with an emphasized emotional character appeared in art. In many cities, the construction of new churches began, and the interiors of old cathedrals were renovated. Interest in sacred art grew significantly, and with it the role of city patrons and patron saints (Freedberg, 1989).

It was at this time that a specific idea was formed: each city had a special patron saint who protected the community from epidemics, natural disasters and wars. To reinforce this myth, paintings, frescoes or sculptures depicting the patron saint were commissioned and installed in key spaces: cathedrals, central squares, town halls. An example is the veneration of San Gennaro in Naples or San Ambrose in Milan. The

idea of “shared holiness” further fueled the feeling of *campanilismo*: the city’s inhabitants felt that they were under “special protection” (Freedberg, 1989, p. 234). Such ideas helped to maintain social unity and a common religious identity, but at the same time they further strengthened prejudices against “foreigners” who came from other Italian cities or regions.

During the Baroque period (17th – early 18th centuries), the city became the scene of numerous theatrical religious and secular celebrations: processions, carnivals, festivals in honor of the patron saint or in honor of the secular dynasty (for example, the Savoy in Piedmont). Baroque architecture, in particular the Roman churches, the palaces in Turin or Naples, reinforced the idea of the power of a particular family or congregation. However, despite the strengthening of the general ideology of Catholicism, local identities did not disappear. In the city-states, their own system of values and differences still existed, which were noticeably manifested in art (Duggan, 2013).

The 19th century was a turning point: on the one hand, the ideas of the *Risorgimento* (“renaissance”) and national movements began to work actively to create a unified Italian state. On the other hand, many residents of different regions (Piedmont, Lombardy, Tuscany, Sicily) still perceived themselves primarily as part of a “small homeland”. The Italian historian and politician Massimo d'Azeglio famously said in the 1860s: “We have created Italy, now we must create Italians” (quoted in Duggan, 2013, p. 145). It indicates that political unification did not immediately destroy regional identities.

It was during this period that *campanilismo* as a concept began to appear more and more frequently in cultural and literary texts, emphasizing a special love for the “bell tower”, the symbol of the city. In the artistic environment, this trend was reflected in the fact that artists and architects developed local styles, rejecting the excessive standardization of all-Italian canons. For example, in the painting of the late 19th century, one can see motifs of peasant life of a certain province, folk festivals, local costumes and topographically recognizable landscapes (Ginsborg, 1990). Such genre

scenes were often demonstrated at regional art exhibitions (*Esposizioni regionali*), organized by local authorities to popularize their region.

In the first half of the 20th century, with the rise of the fascist regime (1922–1943) of Benito Mussolini, the central government tried to reinforce the idea of a single national identity, often using Roman symbols in official propaganda (Roman eagles, fascines, etc.). However, local feelings did not disappear: in many regions strong historical memories of the past remained (for example, in Tuscany - about the Republic, in Venice - about the greatness of the former maritime power) (Duggan, 2013). Even under the authoritarian regime, the idea of *campanilismo* made itself felt, in particular, in cultural initiatives and in the revival of folklore.

After World War II and the establishment of the republican system (1946), Italy experienced a period of economic miracle (1950s–1960s), when a significant part of the population migrated from the south to the north. This exacerbated the issue of identity and led to the fact that local pride in northern cities often turned into outright xenophobia towards migrants from the *Mezzogiorno* (southern regions). At the same time, the feeling of a “small homeland” stimulated the development of various cultural activities that affirmed the uniqueness of local traditions (Ginsborg, 1990).

Thus, *campanilismo* was formed and entrenched in the Italian consciousness as a consequence of centuries-old peculiarities of political-territorial, socio-cultural and religious development. It permeates art at all stages - from the Middle Ages to the present day, from frescoes and sculpture to modern installations or photography that glorify the “small homelands”.

2.2. Artistic language and symbolism of *campanilismo*

The etymology of the word *campanilismo* directly refers to the term *campanile*, a bell tower that usually towers over Italian cities and towns, defining their silhouette. In a medieval city, the bell tower had several functions: it announced religious services, served as a fire or military “alarm”, and also symbolized the presence of the Church or the municipality (in the case of a secular tower) (Paoletti, Radke, 2005, p. 23). It was the tallest building, visible from great distances. For the inhabitants, the “shadow of the bell tower” meant the space where they lived, worked and felt at home. That is why

the bell tower became the personification of local identity, because every citizen associated himself with its contour.

In art, this symbol manifests itself in various ways. Medieval and Renaissance frescoes often included a cityscape in the background dominated by a bell tower (for example, in frescoes depicting the lives of the city's patron saints). In Renaissance painting, cities in the background (say, in scenes of the Annunciation or the Madonna and Child) are also easily identified by the characteristic profile of bell towers (Burke, 1972, p. 58). This served as a visual sign: the artist and the client indicated "their" space, proclaimed their belonging to a particular community.

In addition to the bell tower, city coats of arms play a significant role in the symbolism of *campanilismo*. Every Italian city that had the status of a commune or republic had (and still has) its own coat of arms. It often contained animals (lion, wolf, eagle), plant motifs (lilies - as in Florence), crowns, crosses, as well as reminders of historical events. The coat of arms was fixed on the walls of municipal buildings, minted on coins, reflected in documents and became a symbolic marker of city pride (Najemy, 2006, p. 87). In works of art, coats of arms could be present as part of heraldic decoration (in frescoes, on the facades of palaces), emphasizing the solemnity and authority of the commune.

The allegory of the city also occupied a prominent place in iconography. In particular, in 14th-century Siena, frescoes and paintings with the allegory of "Good and Bad Government" (Ambrogio Lorenzetti, *Allegoria del Buono e del Cattivo Governo*, 1338–1339) in the Palazzo Pubblico were widespread. This cycle did not simply depict urban landscapes, but also conveyed the idea of the city's prosperity under just rule and decline under tyranny. Although there is no direct reference to *campanilismo*, the idea itself of "our city flourishes under good government" is an echo of deep feelings of local identity (Burke, 1972, p. 99).

Patron saints become an important element of symbolism. Most Italian cities have their own canonized patron saints (for example, Saint Catherine is the patron saint of Siena, Saint Mark is the patron saint of Venice, Saint Ambrose is the patron saint of Milan), whose images carry the idea of heavenly protection (Freedberg, 1989, p. 121).

The lives of saints, particularly those associated with a specific city, are reproduced in frescoes, icons, and paintings - these images emphasize the exclusivity of the city, "chosen" by heavenly power.

Within the framework of *campanilismo*, a specific local artistic language is often formed. For example, the Sieneese school of painting of the Proto-Renaissance era (Duccio, Simone Martini) used bright, saturated colors (red, gold and blue shades predominated), refined linearity and graceful contours of figures (Burke, 1972, p. 102). In Florence, on the contrary, the emphasis was on a more voluminous interpretation of figures (starting with Giotto), perspective constructions of space (in the works of Masaccio, Brunelleschi) and a rational approach to composition. Local stylistics were often perceived as "our" method, "our" visual signature, distinguishing the Florentines from the Sieneese or Venetians.

The Venetian school (Bellini, Titian, Veronese, Tintoretto) was famous for its color, the play of light and shadow, the reflection of lagoon landscapes and the love of lush ceremonial scenes. Here the idea was strengthened that Venetian art was something separate from "continental" Italian, because the city itself was built on water and had a different historical and cultural heritage (Paoletti, Radke, 2005, p. 139). Such specificity also absorbs the spirit of *campanilismo*: the emphasis on the unique topography and lifestyle becomes an image that goes beyond the local and identifies the entire community.

As for architecture, even within the same style (Renaissance or Baroque) there were differences related to the choice of materials, building sizes, street layouts, etc. In Siena, for example, the use of dark red bricks created a characteristic appearance of buildings that differed from the lighter facades of Florence. These visual details, which form the "face" of the city, are often transferred into works of art, becoming recognizable codes of local culture (Ginzburg, 1980).

In the 20th and 21st centuries, the symbolism of *campanilismo* has transformed, but has not disappeared. It can be found in posters for local festivals, in photography, graphic design, and street art depicting urban landscapes or historical monuments. City festivals (such as the Palio di Siena) still inspire artists to create posters and souvenirs

with a characteristic style to convey a sense of pride in “their” city (Paoletti and Radke, 2005, p. 240).

Contemporary Italian photographers and multimedia artists sometimes turn to the theme of local identity to express the contrast between historical tradition and the challenges of globalization. For example, projects dedicated to the problems of urbanization often feature the motif of abandoned historic centers of small towns that lose their inhabitants but retain the “bell tower” as an iconic symbol (Ginsborg, 1990). This ambivalence suggests that campanilismo can be both a source of pride and nostalgia for a disappearing tradition.

2.3. Research on individual works and artists

Ambrogio Lorenzetti, “Allegory of Good and Bad Government” (1338–1339),
Siena

One of the most famous examples of the visual representation of local identity

and political ideas is the cycle of frescoes by Ambrogio Lorenzetti, located in the Palazzo Pubblico (Siena, Palazzo Pubblico) (Burke, 1972, p. 99). This work consists of several scenes illustrating the impact of “good” and “bad” government on the city and countryside. The scenes of “Good Government” show a prosperous city with happy residents, lively crafts and an orderly urban life. Although the term *campanilismo* is not mentioned in the frescoes themselves, the Siena depicted is in fact an idealized image of a “community” in harmony. For a 14th-century audience, this was a powerful message: it emphasized the role of the rulers-Podesta and Consul, as well as the collective responsibility of citizens for the good of the city (Najemy, 2006, p. 67).

In the adjacent hall of the Palazzo Pubblico, one can also find frescoes showing the city of Siena under the protection of the Virgin Mary (especially in the works of Simone Martini). This plot illustrates the religious affirmation of *campanilismo*: the city belongs to the Virgin Mary, and its inhabitants are a “chosen” people called to live a life of virtue (Freedberg, 1989). Traditions inherited in the following centuries emphasized that Siena was saved from various disasters (such as plague or enemy invasion) precisely thanks to heavenly protection.

Duccio di Buoninsegna, “Maesta” (1308–1311), Siena

Another example from the same urban culture is Duccio's "Maesta" icon, intended for the high altar of the Siena Cathedral (Burke, 1972, p. 95). This large-scale altarpiece depicts the Virgin Mary on a throne surrounded by angels and saints, and on the reverse, scenes from the life of Christ. Although the "Maesta" is primarily a religious work, its lower part contains an inscription that represents Duccio's prayer to the Virgin Mary asking her to save the city from disaster. This integration of religious imagery and urban pride directly points to *campanilismo*: the city's main shrine becomes a sign of collective identity, and the artist acts as a spokesman for this idea.

Sandro Botticelli, "Spring" (1477–1482) and "The Birth of Venus" (1484–1486),
Florence

Botticelli's works, at first glance, do not contain images of the city as such, but they are inextricably linked to the culture of Florence during the Medici era. “Spring” and “The Birth of Venus” are considered allegorical canvases that glorify the sublime culture of humanism. At the same time, they are closely connected with the ideology of the Florentine court: the customer of these works could have been Lorenzo de' Medici or his entourage (Paoletti, Radke, 2005, p. 131). In this sense, the paintings act not only as an expression of the Renaissance worldview, but also as a manifestation of the greatness of Florence as a “new Athens”, where art, philosophy and beauty flourished under the patronage of rulers who loved their city.

Despite the lack of direct reference to the cityscape or the bell tower, this idea of urban pride is read in the details: symbols of spring, prosperity, and ancient deities hint that Florence is in a period of “bloom.” Renaissance culture, with its emphasis on human dignity and the revival of ancient values, was at the same time a field for competition with other cities, primarily Venice and Milan, for the right to be considered the center of the Italian Renaissance (Najemy, 2006).

Giovanni Bellini, “Madonna and Child with Saints” (San Giobe Altarpiece), 1478–1480, Venice

Bellini, as a representative of the Venetian school, created altarpieces in which a careful analysis of space, light and color defines the unique artistic language of Venice. In the “Altar of San Giobe” we see the Madonna and Child surrounded by saints, and the background is marked by lush architecture, reminiscent of Venetian traditions and wealth (Paoletti, Radke, 2005, p. 163). Although the work itself does not contain an image of a canal or the Doge's Palace, it also traces the special Venetian aesthetics of softness of light and coloristic splendor. This indicates that “Venetianity” was not just a geographical, but also an aesthetic concept, different from, say, the Florentine rational perspective. Such a culture contributed to the formation of *campanilismo* among the Venetians, who perceived their city as “Serenissima” — the clearest republic with a unique aesthetic atmosphere.

Peter Paul Rubens, fresco cycle in the Palazzo del Doge (second quarter of the 17th century), Genoa

Although a Flemish master, Rubens worked in Genoa on commission from local patricians. In his works for the Genoese palaces, Rubens depicted allegories related to the history and myths of Genoa (Paoletti, Radke, 2005, p. 210). This cycle emphasized the idea that the city-state of Genoa had a long heroic tradition dating back to antiquity. The involvement of a foreign, yet internationally renowned artist was evidence of Genoa's ambitions for its cultural status. Such commissions demonstrate how *campanilismo* could manifest itself in the desire to represent the city on the international stage of art and politics.

Machiavelli (second half of the 19th century) and their contribution to local issues

In the period after the unification of Italy (late 19th century), a group of artists known as the “*macchiaioli*” (Italian: *macchiaioli*) developed plein air painting, focusing on simple scenes from the lives of Tuscan peasants, soldiers, and small-town residents (Ginsborg, 1990). Among the representatives of the group were Giovanni Fattori, Silvestro Lega, and Tele Macco Signorelli. Although the *Macchiaioli* were influenced by French impressionism, they maintained a close connection with local realities: their canvases convey the spirit of Tuscan landscapes, the atmosphere of a “small homeland”. Such themes served as a kind of antithesis to the cosmopolitan official art that dominated the academies.

Giorgio de Chirico and the “metaphysical” view of the city Giorgio de Chirico, born in Greece but with Italian family roots, often depicted deserted city squares surrounded by arcades and buildings with long shadows in his “metaphysical” paintings (early 20th century). The sense of alienation and mystery that these landscapes create is, on the one hand, universal for modernist culture, and on the other hand, “Italian” through the characteristic architecture and motifs. Although de Chirico did not set out to glorify any specific city, his style is rooted in the Italian urban environment (Ginsborg, 1990). Here, *campanilismo* manifests itself indirectly: the

artist transforms familiar urban images into metaphysical spaces, while preserving the Italian atmosphere (arcades, statues, towers).

Contemporary art and multimedia projects dedicated to cities In the 21st century, many Italian artists use video art, photography, and installations to understand the historical landscape, local rituals, and the changing urban environment (Gómez, 2009). For example, documentary photography projects that capture the old quarters of Naples or the deserted towns of Sicily are often accompanied by comments about the “small homeland,” nostalgia for the past, and the challenges of the present (Ginsborg, 1990). In some cases, the authors of the works emphasize that these local “roots” are the key to understanding the Italian soul, even when the country is integrated into the European and global space.

Street art is worth mentioning separately: in cities such as Bologna, Rome, Milan, murals with images of historical figures, local heroes or symbolic landscapes are increasingly appearing (Gómez, 2009). This phenomenon began as a social protest or simply a self-expression of street artists, but gradually became a tool for revitalizing neighborhoods. In this way, once neglected suburbs or old neighborhoods receive a “calling card” in the form of a mural, emphasizing their uniqueness. This is a manifestation of campanilismo on a new level: the community associates itself with a specific image painted on the wall.

In addition to individual works, there are thematic exhibitions and festivals dedicated specifically to local identity. For example, exhibitions organized at the Palazzo Strozzi Museum in Florence often focus on the city’s past and the Renaissance as a “golden age”, involving new interpretations of the relevant subjects. The Municipality of Siena, in turn, supports cultural events that reinforce the meaning of the Palio and the associated symbolism of the contradas (Paoletti, Radke, 2005, p. 241). Such events stimulate scholarly and public interest in campanilismo, and also help local communities rethink their history in the context of contemporary challenges - from the tourism industry to digital artistic practices.

The analysis of campanilismo in Italian art shows that this phenomenon grew out of complex historical and political processes - from the era of medieval communes

and republics to the Renaissance and the Unification of Italy. In visual culture, the symbol of the "bell tower" (campanile), city coats of arms, allegories of "good governance", images of patron saints and various ritual practices (such as the Palio di Siena) become iconic markers of local identity. Their artistic elaboration demonstrates how deeply the sense of pride for the "small homeland" is rooted in Italian culture.

Despite a certain romanticization or idealization of the past, campanilismo remains relevant for Italian society today. Contemporary artists turn to local themes and symbolism, seeking either to find authenticity in the age of globalization, or to critically rethink the "bell tower", which can be a carrier not only of pride, but also of narrow-minded isolation. Ultimately, this multidimensionality of campanilismo makes it one of the key cultural factors of Italian artistic life: it reflects the historical experience of a country that has gone from fragmented medieval republics to a modern democratic state integrated into the European space.

CHAPTER 3. ANALYSIS OF SENTIMIENTO DE COMUNIDAD IN SPANISH ART AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

3.1. Historical and cultural context of Spain

The history of Spain is characterized by a complex dynamic of political consolidation and regional disunity. Unlike most European countries, where monarchical centralization occurred relatively early (England, France), the Iberian Peninsula has long been a region of separate kingdoms and territories with significant autonomy (Castilla, Aragón, Navarra, León, Granada, etc.). The process of unification of most of the peninsula under the rule of the Catholic Kings Ferdinand II of Aragon and Isabella I of Castile (late 15th - early 16th centuries) is considered one of the key moments in Spanish history (Kamen, 1964). However, even after the formation of the Spanish monarchy, each region retained its own cultural specificity, legal customs and sometimes even separate institutions, which became the basis for the phenomenon of *sentimiento de comunidad* (“feeling of community”).

A special role in the formation of Spanish identity was played by the process of the Reconquista - the gradual reconquest by Christian states of territories previously controlled by Muslim rulers (8th–15th centuries). With the capture of Granada in 1492, this long historical stage effectively ended. For the Spaniards, that time became one of the most important cultural myths, fueling the idea of a “common destiny” on the path to protecting Christianity and reconquering “historical lands” (Elliott, 2002). However, even during the Reconquista, each kingdom had its own dynasty, laws, army and cultural traditions, which determined the formation of local identities.

As researchers (Moreno, 1997) point out, the idea of a “joint struggle” against Al-Andalus (Muslim possessions) did not always lead to unitarism. On the contrary, in periods when certain kingdoms participated in military operations more actively than others, their pride in their own victories increased. Thus, already in the Middle Ages, a paradox was formed: on the one hand, a certain general Catholic project of consolidation of the peninsula, on the other, a deep awareness of regional differences

and pride in local traditions. This paradox formed the basis of the *sentimiento de comunidad*, since the concept of “community” in Spain is almost always correlated with a specific territory, a historical myth and a set of cultural codes.

Starting from the 16th century, when the Habsburg dynasty (Charles V, Philip II) concentrated power in its hands over vast possessions not only in Europe, but also in overseas colonies (Latin America, the Philippines), Spain became one of the leading powers in the world. This period, known as the “*Siglo de Oro*” (16th–17th centuries), was marked by the flowering of arts and literature: such outstanding authors as Miguel de Cervantes, Lope de Vega, Tirso de Molina, Calderón de la Barca appeared on the scene; in painting, the galaxy of Velázquez, Ribera, Zurbarán, Murillo shone; in sculpture, Gregorio Fernández and other masters (Brown, Elliott, 1991).

At the same time, the royal court in Madrid (as well as the royal courts in Valladolid or Seville during their temporary stays) cultivated the idea of a universal Catholic monarchy, uniting the various lands under Habsburg rule. However, this unification was dynastic rather than entirely unitary. The regions (the Crown of Castile, the Crown of Aragon, etc.) had their own cortes, their own customary rights and a considerable degree of autonomy, especially in the management of internal affairs (Kamen, 1964). In parallel, the idea that Spain was a “community of communities” was strengthened, where there were different peoples united by dynasty and Catholic faith.

In art, these processes were reflected, in particular, in the painting of numerous portraits of kings, aristocrats and saints, in the commissioning of large-scale religious paintings. Also, stage performances were often created at the royal court, where Christian virtues were emphasized and the role of the monarch was glorified. However, if court art mostly promoted the ideology of a “single Catholic monarchy”, then the regions had their own artifacts that emphasized specific traditions. For example, in Catalonia and Valencia, their own dramatic genres developed, and in Andalusia, Baroque religious images became widespread, becoming symbols of local piety (Moreno, 1997).

In the same era, the cult of patron saints of cities and regions became widespread. Each city had its own prominent saints or images of the Virgin Mary, who were

considered “special” for this territory. Therefore, in paintings, sculptures or frescoes, the ideal of the chosenness of “our” city or region was constantly reinforced. This phenomenon is similar to what happened in Italy with the cults of city saints, but the Spanish version was more closely connected with the general monarchical-Catholic ideology of the Habsburgs (Elliott, 2002). As a result, a peculiar interweaving of regional and imperial consciousness took place: the Sevillians were proud of their city and at the same time felt a sense of belonging to the great Catholic empire.

Starting from the 18th century, after the War of the Spanish Succession, the Bourbon dynasty came to power, which in some aspects tried to centralize and modernize state administration (in particular, carrying out new royal reforms, abolishing some privileges, etc.). At the same time, under the influence of the ideas of the Enlightenment, the sciences flourished, academies and libraries were opened, and royal architecture developed (the palace in Madrid, the construction of residences). However, the difference between Castile, Andalusia, Aragon, Catalonia, etc. did not disappear anywhere (Lannon, 1987). Despite centralizing efforts, local nobility and communities preserved their ancient enchanting festivals, folklore, and mythology of the regions.

One of the significant factors in the culture of the 18th century was the desire of some Spanish intellectuals to combine new European ideas with “ancient Spanish traditions” (Herr, 1971). This again activated attention to local customs, some of which (such as festivals in honor of patron saints or festive bullfights) were considered as “national color”, but at the same time in each region had their own specific forms. Accordingly, genre scenes appeared in art (for example, in the engravings of Francisco Goya), showing scenes from everyday life, street fairs, bullfights, etc. Thus, a new aesthetic consciousness was formed, in which folk plots acquired the status of a significant cultural heritage.

In the 19th century, Spain, like most European countries, experienced a wave of liberal revolutions, wars and coups. Periodic changes of power (monarchy, republic, monarchy again) were accompanied by the loss of the last colonies (Cuba, Philippines, Puerto Rico). The internal situation became more complicated: Catalans, Basques,

Andalusians and other communities increasingly expressed a desire to preserve their own cultural and linguistic characteristics (Moreno, 1997). It was in the 19th century that the first Catalan and Basque movements for the “revival” of language and culture were formed. In parallel with this, there was a tendency in art towards a realistic and romantic depiction of regional subjects. Artists such as Vallesquin or José García Ramos recreated scenes from Andalusian streets, rural life in Castile, festive carnivals in Galicia, etc.

At the beginning of the 20th century, especially after the dictatorship of Primo de Rivera (1923–1930) and the Second Spanish Republic (1931–1936), political conflicts intensified, which eventually culminated in the Civil War (1936–1939). General Franco’s victory initiated a 36-year dictatorship (1939–1975), which sought to implement the unitary concept of a “united Spain”. Regional differences were suppressed: the use of Catalan, Basque and Galician languages in public was restricted. However, these prohibitions could not completely destroy local cultures. Underground movements, the emigration of intellectuals, and even internal opposition supported the idea of regional identity (Lannon, 1987).

In post-war art, despite censorship, many artists responded to local themes, often in a veiled way, through symbols. Catalan artists (e.g. Joan Miró, Antoni Tàpies) and Basque artists (Eduardo Chillida, Jorge Oteiza) sought an abstract language that could contain “national” allusions while avoiding direct political content, which was repressed by the regime (Cirlot, 1992).

After Franco's death (1975), Spain entered a period of transformation (La Transición), when democracy was restored and the 1978 Constitution was adopted. One of the most important decisions was decentralization, which resulted in the creation of the so-called “autonomous communities” (Comunidades Autónomas). Catalonia, the Basque Country, Andalusia, Galicia and other regions received broad powers in cultural and educational policy and the management of local affairs (Moreno, 1997). This step stimulated the rapid development of regional cultures, and with them - expressive forms of *sentimiento de comunidad*: from the revival of local holidays and festivals to the official recognition of regional languages and symbols (anthems, flags).

In art, all this was reflected in an explosion of cultural projects, festivals, and exhibitions that emphasized local specificity and historical heritage. This is especially noticeable in regions with powerful national-regional movements: Catalonia (Barcelona became an influential cultural center), the Basque Country (Bilbao with the “Guggenheim Museum” as a symbol of modernization), Valencia, Andalusia (famous flamenco festivals, Semana Santa celebrations). Gradually, *sentimiento de comunidad* ceased to be only a cultural phenomenon and also acquired political weight, in particular in the context of movements for increased autonomy or even independence (Elliott, 2018).

3.2. Visual features and artistic symbolism

Among the most visible visual manifestations of *sentimiento de comunidad* is the use of regional symbols in painting, posters, and design. In Catalonia, the emblem of four red stripes on a gold background (the *Senyera*) is widely known, which can be found both in contemporary art installations and on the canvases of artists who defend the idea of Catalan identity (Moreno, 1997). A similar function is served by the Basque flag of *Icurrenha* (red background, green oblique cross and white cross on top) or the Andalusian flag with the image of Hercules and lions. These visual codes are firmly entrenched in the minds of local residents and often appear in works of art as a “reference to ours”.

In addition to flags, images of local heroes, historical figures or legendary kings are actively used (for example, Jaime I the Conqueror in Aragon/Valencia, *Villalba Agony* among the Basques, *Christ of the Great Miracles* in Andalusia, etc.). In paintings or sculptures dedicated to these heroes, patriotic pathos prevails, which correlates with the “sacred history” of each region. Even in the era of modernism or postmodernism, artists often return to traditional icons, rethinking them in new styles (Cirlot, 1992).

As in Italy, religion is a major pillar of Spanish cultural identity. The tradition of Catholic processions and the cult of the Virgin Mary and numerous saints is particularly

strong (Lannon, 1987). For example, in Seville, the cult of the Virgin Mary La Macarena has become the city's calling card: every year during Holy Week (Semana Santa), grand processions take place, in which the figure of the Virgin Mary is depicted wearing a crown, adorned with jewels, and accompanied by hundreds of brotherhoods (cofradías). This culture has gone far beyond the purely religious sphere and has become a symbol of Andalusian community, exporting through the media and tourism the idea of the "Andalusian soul" (Moreno, 1997, p. 82). In the visual arts – painting, photography, graphic design – this image (and similar ones) are repeatedly captured as the quintessence of regional pride.

Another example is the "Moros y Cristianos" (Moors and Christians) tradition in Valencia or Murcia, where theatrical performances recreate scenes of battles between Christian and Muslim armies, while emphasizing the syncretic cultural heritage of the region (Anderson, 1983). This is also often the subject of artistic projects that actualize local historical subjects, giving them a contemporary sound (for example, street murals or installations at festivals).

A significant part of the *sentimiento de comunidad* is folklore customs: dances (Sevillana, sardana, muineira), music (flamenco, Gaeta in Galicia), costumes (traditional Basque, Andalusian, Catalan, etc.). In works of art dedicated to these subjects, artists usually show the splendor of costumes, expressiveness of movements, and the colorful atmosphere of fairs and festivals (Moreno, 1997). Thus, the drawings and paintings of Joaquín Sorolla often celebrate the light and color of the Spanish coast, capture scenes of folk festivals, weddings, and "ferias," demonstrating the richness of local traditions.

Folklore rituals are also embodied in contemporary performance, video art, and photography. A new generation of artists, such as Cristina García Roderó, creates documentary photo series about local rituals, processions, and festivals, showing how they unite the community (Gómez, 2009). In such works, *sentimiento de comunidad* becomes not just a "theme" but a living phenomenon, born from the interaction of the inhabitants, their costumes, music, dance, and sacred or secular images.

Starting from the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Spain was influenced by European modernist movements. It was especially noticeable in Catalonia, where Catalan modernism (*Modernisme català*) was formed, associated with the architecture of Antoni Gaudí, José Puig y Cadafalco, Luis Domenech and Montaner. Barcelona became a laboratory of the Art Nouveau style with a local bias. While the Art Nouveau school dominated in France, and the Secession in Austria, Catalan modernism added local decorative motifs, references to medieval Catalan architecture and folklore (Cirlot, 1992). In this way, the idea of *sentimiento de comunidad* acquired a new dimension: the architecture of Barcelona became a living manifesto of Catalan cultural distinctiveness.

The avant-garde art of the first half of the 20th century also did not bypass the theme of regional identity. In the works of Pablo Picasso, Juan Gris, Salvador Dalí, Joan Miró, although the cosmopolitan avant-garde aesthetics dominate, symbols typical of their native regions can be traced in some places. Thus, in Dalí's later works, landscapes of the Costa Brava (Catalonia) are found, which serve as the basis for his surrealist compositions. Miró uses Catalan symbolism in a number of works (the famous serpentine spring-like sign, referring to human towers - "castells", as well as color combinations inspired by the Catalan flag) (Cirlot, 1992, p. 44).

After the transition to democracy (1975–1978) and the emergence of autonomous governments, artists from different regions began to address the theme of local identity much more openly, understanding it in the context of globalization and European integration. Thus, in the Basque Country, there was a boom in artistic initiatives that emphasized the ancient culture and language of the Basques. In the projects of Eduardo Chillida and Jorge Oteiza, a philosophical and aesthetic reflection is traced, where the nature of the Basques, its mountains, and the space of the Atlantic coast become symbols of the national cosmos (Elliott, 2018).

In Andalusia, visual artists are taking up the themes of flamenco, bullfighting and the synthesis of Arab-Christian heritage (for example, in the photo reports of Cristina García Rodero), showing how these traditions are reflected in the modern world (Gómez, 2009). In Catalonia, a trend of politically engaged street art is

developing, using inscriptions in Catalan, national colors and references to historical figures (Moreno, 1997). Thus, the *sentimiento de comunidad* becomes a powerful generator of plots and visual images, where history, myth and contemporary political realities are intertwined into a single whole.

3.3. Comparative analysis with *campanilismo*

Analysis of *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad* shows that both are forms of local pride that have deep historical roots and find expression in art. In Italy, the concept of *campanilismo* is often associated with an urban (communal) identity that was formed in the era of medieval city-states (Ginzburg, 1980; Paoletti, Radke, 2005). In Spain, *sentimiento de comunidad* is usually associated with a wider regional scale (Catalonia, Andalusia, the Basque Country, Galicia), although in some cases it can also refer to a specific city (for example, Seville or Valencia) (Moreno, 1997).

The common feature is that both phenomena include historical memory as an important element of self-identification. Italian cities preserve the memory of heroic pages of republican rule or of influential patrons (For example, Florence, Siena, Venice), while Spanish regions constantly refer to medieval kingdoms, to the Reconquista, to the traditions of the "golden age". Artists, architects, sculptors use these subjects, creating a symbolic space where history and modernity collide.

Another coincidence is the important role of religious cults and patron saints. In both Italy and Spain, the Catholic tradition was so deeply rooted that city or regional saints became the "calling cards" of the local community (Freedberg, 1989). In Italy, examples include the *culto di Santa Caterina* in Siena or the *festa di San Gennaro* in Naples. In Spain, *Semana Santa* in Seville, the cults of the *Virgen del Pilar* in Zaragoza (Aragon), and the *Virgen de Montserrat* in Catalonia. These images often become central themes for works of art (from frescoes and paintings to sculptures and festival posters).

Despite their many parallels, *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad* also have significant differences. First, the scale. Italian *campanilismo* is mostly focused on

the city, the “shadow of the bell tower” (*campanile*). The nature of this phenomenon goes back to medieval communes, where the city was the main political and economic unit (Paoletti, Radke, 2005). In contrast, Spanish *sentimiento de comunidad* is mainly associated with the concept of an “autonomous community”, which usually covers larger territories, has its own historical kingdoms or provinces (Catalonia, Andalusia, the Basque Country, Galicia, etc.). Thus, while in Italy the key center of pride is a specific city (Florence, Siena, Venice), in Spain it is an entire region, which may include several large cities and different landscapes (Moreno, 1997).

Second, the historical trajectories are different. In Italy, political fragmentation continued until the 19th century, and unification occurred relatively late. In contrast, Spain was formally a “unitary monarchy” from the late 15th to early 16th centuries, but in practice each region retained its own laws and customs for a long time. This meant that Italian *campanilismo* often has a connotation of long-term independence (republican traditions, specific political institutions), while Spanish *sentimiento de comunidad* is more of an emphasis on cultural identity within a larger state (Kamen, 1964; Moreno, 1997).

Third, symbolic load. In Italy, visual images are often tied to specific urban landscapes: bell towers, palaces, architectural ensembles, while in Spain, regional iconography is mainly based on larger historical myths (Reconquista, *Católicos Reyes*, Habsburg Empire), symbols (regional flags, coats of arms), folkloric festivals (*Moros y Cristianos*, *Fallas*, *Feria de Abril*). Although the city itself (Seville, Valencia, Barcelona) can also become a marker of local identity, the main emphasis is usually on the diversity of the entire region.

In both Italy and Spain, art plays a fundamental role in constructing and sustaining local pride. High Renaissance or Baroque art, frescoes, paintings, icons, and architectural masterpieces were often commissioned by local elites, from municipal councils in Italy to city councils or cathedral chapters in Spain (Ginsborg, 1990; Lannon, 1987). New artistic languages emerge in the modern era (Impressionism, Expressionism, Cubism, Surrealism), but they are often enriched by local elements. For example, Catalan modernism acquired distinctive features that were distinct from

French Art Nouveau; Italian futurism contained allusions to the “Italian spirit” in the context of national renewal.

The role of art in supporting *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad* is also evident in the contemporary festival movement, exhibition initiatives, and museums. In Siena (Italy), the Palio remains the main event, in Venice, the Carnival and the Biennale, and in Spain, a huge number of regional festivals such as Las Fallas in Valencia, Feria de Abril in Seville, San Fermín in Pamplona, etc. (Anderson, 1983). Although these events have deep historical roots, contemporary artists are reinterpreting them, often criticizing commercialization or tourist exploitation, while at the same time affirming the importance of local solidarity and traditions.

In both countries, Italy and Spain, the phenomena of *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad* are today under the influence of globalization, mass tourism and digital culture. On the one hand, local festivals and traditions, which were once the internal affairs of the community, become a mass spectacle for tourists. This can lead to commercialization and a certain loss of “authenticity” (Hobsbawm, Ranger, 1983). On the other hand, the growing interest in “local flavor” stimulates the preservation and restoration of folk crafts, historical monuments, and folklore customs.

In art, multifaceted projects are emerging that critically reflect on the phenomenon of local identity. For example, in Catalonia, a number of artists analyze political confrontations related to the idea of independence. In the Basque Country, artists raise the topic of violence (due to the activities of the terrorist organization ETA in the past) and the search for ways of reconciliation, where culture becomes one of the tools (Elliott, 2018). In Italy, the problems of the southern regions (Mezzogiorno), economic inequality, the phenomenon of the Northern League - all this becomes the object of criticism and reflection by artists who turn to the symbols of *campanilismo* to show the contrasts and paradoxes of modern Italy (Ginsborg, 1990).

Thus, *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad* do not remain static phenomena, but are constantly transformed under the influence of global processes. However, their ability to reproduce a “sense of community” through art testifies to the

power of cultural traditions and how deeply local identities are rooted in historical memory and aesthetic practices.

A comparative study of *campanilismo* in Italy and *sentimiento de comunidad* in Spain opens up wide possibilities for further research, as both phenomena allow us to understand how local identities coexist with national and supranational projects (the European Union, the global cultural market). Works of art, from medieval frescoes to contemporary installations, reflect complex configurations of power, historical experience, and collective imagination (Anderson, 1983).

Methodologically, this comparative analysis can be useful for cultural scientists, art historians, anthropologists, sociologists, and political scientists, as it demonstrates how artistic representation and social practices (festivals, carnivals, the cult of saints) shape the sense of “we” and set symbolic boundaries between “ours” and “others.” In addition, studying how *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad* function in the age of digital media could become a separate topic of research: social networks, online communities, virtual exhibitions, and digital archives provide new forms for maintaining or transforming local pride.

A comparative approach also helps to identify universal mechanisms of local self-identification, such as:

1. Symbolic emphasis on history (cults of saints, historical figures, mythology of origin).
2. Materialization through space (architecture, city holidays, landscape).
3. Creation and periodic updating of folklore and carnival traditions (Palio, Semana Santa, Fallas).
4. The creative interpretation of contemporary artists, who, by addressing local subjects, can either uphold tradition or critically rethink it (Gómez, 2009).

Based on this, *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad* can be considered varieties of regionalism or localism, arising within the framework of larger national projects, but having their own aesthetic and social autonomy. In both cases, art becomes

a place (forum) where issues of collective memory, identity and cultural politics are discussed. That is why their comparison is extremely important for understanding the European cultural mosaic, built on a centuries-old history of interaction between the local and the national, the religious and the secular, the traditional and the modern.

The study of *sentimiento de comunidad* in Spanish art reveals a complex interweaving of historical, cultural and political factors that shaped regional identity. From the formation of medieval kingdoms to the modern autonomous structure, Spain has always been a “unity in diversity”, with each region having its own traditions, language, customs and myths of origin. In art, this was expressed through religious images, the cult of saints, architectural projects, folkloric and historical subjects, as well as in modern and postmodern trends, which often made references to local characteristics.

Comparing *sentimiento de comunidad* with the Italian *campanilismo* reveals significant commonalities in that both phenomena reinforce local pride and are reflected in centuries-old artistic traditions, yet differ in scale (city versus region) and historical trajectories (late unification of Italy versus early but incomplete centralism of Spain). In the modern era of globalization, both phenomena are facing powerful challenges, but at the same time they are also receiving new opportunities for self-presentation and creative reinvention.

Thus, *sentimiento de comunidad* in Spain and *campanilismo* in Italy should be considered not only as archaic remnants of the past, but primarily as dynamic cultural constructs that continue to influence the lives of contemporary societies, shaping their visual order and determining the nature of the interaction between art and collective memory. Further research in this area could include a deeper analysis of specific artists, performances, local festivals or digital art projects, revealing new aspects of the “sense of community” in the European cultural space.

CONCLUSIONS

The conducted study of the depiction of community in European art covers two important cultural concepts that reflect local identity – campanilismo in Italy and

sentimiento de comunidad in Spain. The analysis of the historical and cultural context, artistic language, symbolism and comparative consideration of these phenomena allows us to draw a number of important conclusions that not only reveal the essence of local pride, but also emphasize its relevance in modern conditions of globalization.

The study showed that both phenomena have deep historical roots, dating back to the Middle Ages. In Italy, the political fragmentation of city-states contributed to the formation of a unique urban identity, when each city, thanks to its autonomous institutions, traditions and competition with other centers, developed its own cultural heritage. The symbolism of the bell tower, which became the etymological source of the concept of campanilismo, reflected the idea of “our city” as the main focus of collective memory and pride (Ginzburg, 1980; Paoletti & Radke, 2005).

In Spain, the process of unification of the kingdoms and the subsequent centralization of power did not eliminate regional differences, but on the contrary, contributed to the consolidation of a sense of community within each region. The Reconquista, the cult of patron saints, folk traditions and popular rituals created the foundation on which the concept of sentimiento de comunidad was built. This phenomenon reflects not only historical unity, but also the multifaceted nature of cultural traditions that retained their uniqueness within the framework of a single state (Kamen, 1964; Moreno, 1997).

One of the key findings of the study is the identification of common mechanisms through which art constructs and sustains a sense of community. Both concepts – campanilismo and sentimiento de comunidad – are based on historical memory, the use of symbols (architectural monuments, coats of arms, religious images) and ritual, which serve as a vehicle for collective identity. Religious symbolism, images of patron saints, participation in traditional celebrations (for example, the Palio di Siena or Semana Santa) create a powerful visual language that reinforces the sense of “uniqueness” of each community.

At the same time, the results of the comparative analysis indicate significant differences between these two phenomena. Campanilismo is predominantly urban in nature, focusing on individual cities and their traditions, which were formed over many

centuries in the context of the political fragmentation of Italy. In this case, an important aspect is the competition between city-states, which affects the choice of artistic images, compositional solutions and architectural forms. In contrast, the *sentimiento de comunidad* in Spain is revealed at the regional level, where historical processes of unification and centralization are intertwined with the richness of regional traditions. Regional identity in Spain is characterized by a variety of cultural codes, linguistic features and religious customs, which are reflected in art through the widespread use of folkloric motifs and symbols characteristic of each region.

One of the most important conclusions of the work is that art plays a role not only in reflecting, but also in actively constructing local identity. In both the case of *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad*, works of art serve as a means of preserving historical memory, maintaining traditions, and creating symbolic codes that define “our” environment. This is confirmed both by classical works of the Middle Ages, Renaissance, and Baroque, and by contemporary multimedia projects that analyze and rethink traditional motifs in light of the contemporary challenges of globalization.

Contemporary artists, turning to digital technologies, social networks and new media, not only preserve traditional symbols, but also reinterpret them, creating new forms of visual expression. This allows adapting cultural heritage to modern conditions, ensuring a lively dialogue between the past and the present. Thus, art becomes a tool for supporting regional identity, as well as a platform for critical reflection on the processes of globalization.

The practical significance of the research lies in the possibility of applying the obtained results to develop cultural strategies aimed at preserving and popularizing regional heritage. In the context of globalization, when cultural unification can lead to the loss of the uniqueness of local traditions, the preservation of local symbols and rituals acquires particular importance. The results of the work can become the basis for developing cultural development programs aimed at supporting local festivals, restoring historical monuments and stimulating tourism based on cultural authenticity.

In addition, the study makes a significant contribution to academic science, as it allows integrating methods of historical and art analysis, comparative research and content analysis of visual symbolism. This contributes to the development of new conceptual approaches to the study of collective memory, cultural identity and social processes in the European context. The results can be used as a theoretical basis for further research in the field of cultural studies, sociology, art history and related disciplines.

Promising areas for further research include analyzing the impact of digital technologies on the transformation of traditional cultural codes, investigating the role of social networks in the formation of modern local identity, and expanding the comparative analysis to other European countries. Such research will contribute to a deeper understanding of how local communities adapt to the conditions of globalization and how traditional symbols are integrated into modern cultural processes.

Summing up the results of the work, it can be noted that the study of the phenomena of *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad* allows us to reveal the multidimensionality of the processes of formation of local identity in Europe. Despite the difference in historical trajectories and the scale of manifestation, both phenomena demonstrate the importance of preserving historical memory, the use of symbolic means and the role of art as a catalyst for cultural dialogue.

The findings indicate that art, regardless of the era, remains a powerful means of expressing collective identity, capable not only of preserving cultural heritage, but also of contributing to its dynamic transformation in the conditions of the modern world. Thus, the results of the study have both theoretical and practical significance, as they contribute to the development of the concept of local identity and suggest ways to support it through cultural initiatives.

Overall, this work makes a significant contribution to understanding how artistic practices construct and preserve a sense of community, which is critical for ensuring cultural diversity and social cohesion. Uncovering the mechanisms of local pride formation, reflected through *campanilismo* and *sentimiento de comunidad*, allows not

only to deepen scientific knowledge about historical and contemporary cultural processes, but also creates a platform for developing strategies for preserving cultural heritage in conditions of rapid socio-economic change.

Thus, the conclusions of the work confirm the need for a comprehensive approach to the analysis of local phenomena in art, which allows combining historical and art methods with modern research practices to create a complete picture of the processes of forming collective memory and cultural identity. The results of the study can become the basis for further scientific explorations and practical initiatives aimed at preserving and developing unique regional traditions, which are an integral part of the European cultural heritage.

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